

Isomerization of β -pinene in the Vapour Phase over Alumina Catalyst : Influence of Partial Pressure of Nitrogen and Pyridine

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Manuscript received 14 September 1981, accepted 21 July 1982

The isomerization of β -pinene in the vapour phase over alumina catalyst has been studied in the presence of nitrogen and pyridine. The isomerization proceeds via two parallel paths, one giving bicyclic products such as α -pinene and camphene and the other giving rise to monocyclic menthadienes such as dipentene, terpinolene, α -terpinene and γ -terpinene. Nitrogen acts as a diluent while pyridine functions as a diluent and as a poison. As a result, it affects the formation of different products to different extent.

The isomerization of β -pinene over alumina follows a second order kinetics. Based on the experimental facts a tentative mechanism, in terms of carbonium ion intermediates, has been proposed.

β -PINENE is a bicyclic mono-olefinic mono-terpene and occurs along with α -pinene in varying proportions in a majority of essential oils derived from Coniferae¹. The first quality Indian turpentine from *Pinus longifolia* contains about 10% β -pinene, the rest being α -pinene (40%) and 3-carene (50%)².

Steinbach *et al*³ reported the thermal isomerization of β -pinene at 160°, while Sully⁴ effected a near quantitative conversion of it into myrcene in the temperature range of 580-750°. Isomerizations of β -pinene over minerals, salts and acids are patented⁵. Verghese⁶ investigated the transformations of β -pinene into monocyclic compounds using phosphoric acid.

The present investigation was undertaken to study the influence of nitrogen and hydrogen on the isomerization of β -pinene over alumina, to determine the kinetics of isomerization and to suggest a tentative mechanism for the formation of the various products.

Experimental

Preparation of materials :

Alumina : Alumina was prepared by hydrolyzing aluminium isopropoxide with distilled water⁷. The precipitated aluminium hydroxide was filtered through a Buchner funnel, washed thoroughly with water, cut into cakes, dried at 120° for 24 hr. The material was activated at 550° in a stream of dry air for 24 hr. The activated material was crushed and ground into powder and sieved. The 40-60 mesh fraction was used for all purposes.

β -Pinene : β -Pinene (Hercules Powder Co., USA) was further fractionated and the liquid distilling at 165°/760 mm was collected and stored in brown bottles. The purity was established to be better than 99% by gas chromatography.

Pyridine : Pyridine (B.D.H. AnalaR) was refluxed over KOH pellets and distilled through an efficient fractionating column with careful exclusion of moisture and the material distilling at 115.5° was collected. The purity was checked by gas chromatographic analysis.

***n*-Butylamine :** *n*-Butylamine used was obtained from B.D.H. It was purified by fractional distillation (b.p. 78°).

Butter yellow : This was prepared by diazotization of aniline and coupling with dimethylaniline at 4°. The dye was purified by column chromatography, crystallized and recrystallized from *iso*-octane.

Nitrogen : Nitrogen (Indian Oxygen Co.) was purified by passing successively through a silica gel drying tower, a tube containing freshly reduced copper turnings kept at 400°, another silica gel tower and finally through a trap cooled in liquid oxygen.

Apparatus and procedure : The reactions were carried out at atmospheric pressure in a fixed bed pyrex flow type reactor, 50 cm long and 1.5 cm internal diameter. The pre-heater was made in the form of a spiral wound uniformly around the reactor covering half of its length, to ensure complete vapourisation of the liquid before entering

the reactor tube. Above the catalyst (5 g) bed pyrex glass beads (4 mm diameter) were placed to a height of 5 cm. The reactor tube was inserted into a furnace, a cylindrical steel tube of internal diameter 4 cm, coated with a thin layer of asbestos, wound uniformly with a nichrome wire and heated electrically to the requisite temperature.

Nitrogen was carefully metered through a precision Hoke valve and its flow rate was measured with a soap film flow meter. Various partial pressures of pyridine were achieved by mixing it with β -pinene in different proportions.

To regenerate and activate the catalyst, it was heated prior to each run for 8 hr in a current of air at 500° until no oxides of carbon were detected in the exit gas. The reactant liquid was fed into the reactor by a constant speed infusion pump. The liquid products collected for the first 15 min of each run (which normally covers 1 hr) were discarded and analysis was made only of the products collected after this time. This was to ensure the attainment of steady state over the catalyst and also to set right any temperature fluctuations.

The liquid products were identified using a Perkin-Elmer infracord spectrophotometer Model-137 and a Perkin-Elmer Vapour Fractometer Model-154 D. They were estimated using a Perkin-Elmer column K, consisting of a two metre column of carbowax on chromosorb. The column temperature for the best resolution within a reasonable time was found to be 115° with hydrogen inlet pressure of 15 psi with TCD detector.

For the identification of different peaks in the chromatogram, retention times for the different compounds were found by introducing authentic samples. For quantitative analysis, synthetic mixtures containing the compounds in varying proportions were introduced and calibration curves relating the concentration with peak heights were drawn. Since the peaks obtained were sharp and symmetrical, peak heights were used as a measure of concentration. All chromatograms for calibration purposes were taken on the same day as a special precaution. Various compounds identified in this investigation are α -pinene, camphene, dipentene, terpinolene, α - and γ -terpinenes. Since the concentration of individual menthadienes is too small, they are grouped together as menthadienes.

The surface area (BET), pore volume, and the average pore radius of the catalyst were determined from low temperature adsorption of nitrogen⁸. The pulse flow technique of Eberly^{9,10} was used to measure the heat of adsorption of pyridine in the temperature range of 180-250°. The total acidity of the catalyst was determined by *n*-butylamine titration method using butter yellow as indicator. All these values are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Influence of particle size: In order to evaluate the influence of transport processes on the rate of

TABLE 1—SURFACE PROPERTIES OF ALUMINA

Surface properties	Values
Surface area (BET), m ² /g	130.00
Pore volume, ml/g	0.4530
Average pore radius, rA	55.00
Heat of adsorption of pyridine, kcal/mole	17.60
Total acidity, meq/g	0.6450

isomerization of β -pinene, the reaction was studied over three different particle sizes and the results are presented in Table 2. This table illustrates the particle size of the catalyst, their corresponding activities in the isomerization of β -pinene, and the measured values of the effectiveness factor, which is equal to the ratio of the actual reaction rate to the reaction rate with no diffusion limitation, obtained on the smallest catalyst particle size of 60-80 mesh.

TABLE 2—INFLUENCE OF PARTICLE SIZE ON THE OVERALL CONVERSION OF β -PINENE

Particle size	Activity of the catalyst (% mole of β -pinene converted)	η measured
Pellets, 5 x 5 mm	66.00	66/78 = 0.85
Powder, 40-60 mesh	75.00	75/78 = 0.96
Powder, 60-80 mesh	78.00	78/78 = 1.00

It has been pointed out by Weisz¹¹ that diffusion effects are negligible when η exceeds 0.95. The catalyst of particle size 40-60 mesh for which η equals 0.96 is almost completely free from diffusion limitation (Table 2). Since the 60-80 mesh catalyst gave rise to large pressure drop across the catalyst bed causing operational difficulties, all the runs were carried out using 40-60 mesh catalyst.

Effect of partial pressure: The overall conversion of β -pinene at various partial pressures of pyridine at 232° is illustrated in Fig. 1. The result obtained in presence of inert diluent nitrogen is also plotted in the same figure for comparison. The distribution of products in the presence of nitrogen and pyridine is given in Figs. 2 and 3, respectively. In the presence of nitrogen, the overall conversion of β -pinene increases with increasing partial pressure of β -pinene upto 0.8 atm (Fig. 1). Above this value the conversion is independent of it. The catalytically active sites are incompletely filled below 0.8 atm and saturated with respect to β -pinene molecules beyond this value and hence increase of partial pressure of β -pinene has no effect on the rate.

Pyridine suppresses the rate of isomerization more significantly than nitrogen. For instance, the amount of β -pinene undergoing conversion in their absence is 80%. At a partial pressure of 0.15 atm, the amounts reacted are reduced to 77% and 52% by nitrogen and pyridine, respectively. Nitrogen acts only as a diluent. Pyridine being a base adsorbs preferentially to β -pinene over both Brønsted and Lewis acid sites with chemical

Fig. 1. Effect of partial pressure of nitrogen and pyridine on the overall conversion of α -pinene. Temp. 232°; contact time = 0.70 hr.

reactions. It is presumed that it neutralizes the Brönsted acid sites with the formation of pyridinium ion and coordinates with the electron deficient aluminium atom (Lewis acid). As a result of these two reactions, the active sites essential for the isomerization of β -pinene are not available and therefore the conversion falls significantly.

Increase of partial pressure of nitrogen affects the formation of products almost equally (Fig. 2). As the conversion of β -pinene decreases with increasing partial pressure of nitrogen, the concentration of products falls.

Fig. 2. Effect of partial pressure of nitrogen on formation of products. Temp. 232°; contact time = 0.70 hr.

Pyridine, unlike nitrogen, suppresses the formation of different products differently (Fig. 3). For

Fig. 3. Effect of partial pressure of pyridine on the formation of products. Temp. 232°; contact time = 0.70 hr.

instance, in the absence of pyridine the concentrations of α -pinene, menthadienes and camphene in the liquid products are 27, 24 and 38%, respectively. Increase in the partial pressure of pyridine from 0 to 0.15 atm decreases these products to 11, 4 and 28%, respectively. Pyridine inhibits the formation of menthadienes to a greater extent than the other two products. From these observations it may be concluded that pyridine inhibits the skeletal isomerization of β -pinene (leading to the formation of menthadienes) more significantly than the double bond isomerization (that gives rise to α -pinene). Camphene formation involving the bridged ring structure is also less affected.

Kinetics: The kinetics of isomerization of β -pinene over alumina has been found to follow a second order kinetics by plotting $\left(\frac{1}{1-x_A}\right)$ against

contact time, W/F_A , where W is the weight of catalyst and F_A is the flow rate of β -pinene per gram of the catalyst (Fig. 4). The rate constants computed from the slopes of the straight line plots are 187.15 and 547.33 litres mole⁻¹ hour⁻¹ at 180 and 232°, respectively. The activation energy was calculated to be 5.1 kcal/mole.

Mechanism: It has been well established that alumina surface contains both Brönsted and Lewis acid sites. Several mechanisms have been proposed for the isomerization of olefins over solid acid catalysts. These include the carbonium ion theory of Whitmore^{1a} and hydrogen switch mechanism of Turkevich and Smith^{1b}. Pines and Haag^{1c} have proposed that the isomerization proceeds through an intermediate π -complex of the olefin and a proton from the catalyst. All these mechanisms assume proton addition to the olefinic double bond accompanied by a subsequent or simultaneous proton elimination from another part of the carbonium ion thus formed.

Fig. 4. Second order plots, temp. 180° and 232°.

Carbonium ions on the surface of solid acid catalysts have been identified by Leftin and Hermana¹⁵. Osaki and Kimura¹⁶ have suggested a proton donor-acceptor mechanism for butene isomerization over solid acid catalysts, either by Brönsted acid sites on the surface of the catalysts or by the carbonium ions formed by the adsorption of olefins on the Lewis sites serving as proton donors.

The isomerization of β -pinene (1) over alumina will be interpreted in terms of carbonium ion intermediates adsorbed on the catalyst surface. It undergoes three types of reactions as outlined in the scheme. Initially the catalyst surface interacts with the double bond of β -pinene molecule resulting in the formation of the carbonium ion (2). This stable tertiary carbonium ion rearranges to a less stable secondary carbonium ion (3) by ring expansion. Carbonium ion (3) undergoes Wagner-Meerwein rearrangement resulting in the formation of camphene (5) through a stable tertiary carbonium ion (4).

Carbonium ion (2) changes into a stable allylic system by elimination of a proton leading to the formation of α -pinene (6). Carbonium ions (2) and (3) may also rearrange to monocyclic carbonium ion (7) by ring opening. This on subsequent elimination of a proton from the appropriate carbon atom gives dipentene (8) and/or terpinolene (9). The exocyclic double bond in terpinolene further isomerizes to endocyclic positions giving rise to α -terpinene (10) and γ -terpinene (11).

Scheme

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